

Deliverable 7.5

Plan for continued communication with stakeholders

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Continued Stakeholder Engagement

1. Introduction

This report outlines the development and implementation of an interactive platform (FIT4FOOD2030 Knowledge Hub) and Sustainable Food Systems Network, which were developed as part of Deliverable 7.5 “*Continued Stakeholder Engagement*” under Work Package 7 (WP7 – Communication, dissemination and future engagement). This deliverable is closely linked to Task 7.6 “*Development of plan for the continued engagement with stakeholders*”, which focuses on the sustainability of the stakeholder network and the FOOD 2030 Platform beyond the duration of FIT4FOOD2030. It aims to continue the commitment of stakeholders at multiple levels. Therefore, both the Knowledge Hub and Sustainable Food Systems Network aspire to maintain the project’s outreach and ensure a stable engagement between different stakeholders not only within European but also international food systems. This deliverable is closely linked and will be based on Task 7.6 previously outlined in Deliverable 7.2.

To ensure the communication between stakeholders, FIT4FOOD2030 established the FOOD 2030 Platform. It is a multi-stakeholder platform (City Labs and Food Labs, Policy Labs, and the EU Think Tank) which facilitated stakeholder’s interaction and cooperation. A shift from the *FOOD 2030 Platform* to the *Sustainable Food Systems Network* occurred with the need to make the communication two-sided, i.e. move from communication to engagement. The main advantages of this new virtual platform are more instructiveness, transparency, and openness to anyone. Apart from the communication facilitation, the Sustainable Food Systems Network aims to disseminate the project’s outcomes of which the hands-on materials for future-proofing Europe’s food systems are located on the Knowledge Hub, which is an online repository of the Tools for Transformation developed during the project. These practical tools and guidelines aim to facilitate the collaboration between key stakeholders in the food system and nourish long-term efforts to create resilient and sustainable food systems with well-integrated responsible research and innovation practices. While the process and (technical) development of the Knowledge Hub itself is laid out in this document, the actual tools and resources within are in more detail described on the Knowledge Hub itself.

2. Purpose

The FIT4FOOD2030 communication WP aims, on the one hand, to increase visibility and promote awareness of the project, including the FOOD 2030 policy framework, and advocate for the importance of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and systems thinking for food system transformation to a wide range of stakeholders and audiences. On the other hand, the aim is to engage stakeholders in a more targeted, hence meaningful way, to enhance the impact of some of the project’s specific activities and outputs.

Maintaining the engagement between different stakeholders after the project’s ending presents a challenge. Due to the complex nature of the project, different stakeholders at multiple levels were involved in the project’s activities which soon revealed a problem of identifying specific interests at each of the levels (local, national and European) as well as an adequate channel for communication. Without a well-developed plan for continued communication between stakeholders, it would be hard to achieve and sustain their collaboration. Besides the

challenge of connecting different actors in food systems, there is also a need to discover ways to disseminate valuable project's outputs and increase their reach.

The objective of the Plan for the Continued Engagement with Stakeholders is to build upon the Task 7.2 *“Development and implementation of multi-level stakeholder engagement plan”*. The main goal is to support the sustainability of the FOOD 2030 platform beyond the duration of FIT4FOOD2030. For that purpose, an engagement plan has been developed, based on the learnings from the stakeholder engagement and aiming for the continued commitment of stakeholders at multiple levels. Two interactive platforms were created – the Knowledge Hub as a repository of practical tools and guidelines which came out of the project, and an interactive online platform Sustainable Food Systems Network.

The objective of the (continued) stakeholder engagement plan, for which a linkage between Tasks 7.2 and 7.6 is foreseen, is threefold:

- To further and more meaningfully engage local and national stakeholders at multiple levels, focusing on the food system and the FOOD 2030 agenda;
- To reshape the FOOD 2030 Platform so that it becomes a two-way communication platform, providing additional opportunities for stakeholder engagement. This will ensure continued and increased engagement in the FOOD 2030 Platform beyond the life of the FIT4FOOD2030 project;
- To amplify the outreach and impact of specific project outputs and activities through the engagement with specific audiences, primarily via the Platform.

3. Task 7.6 – Development of plan for continued engagement with stakeholders

The FOOD 2030 Platform, in its previous form, lacked meaningful elements to foster engagement in a way that allowed stakeholders to reap the benefits from the Platform directly. Therefore, as laid out in the stakeholder engagement plan under Deliverable 7.2, Task 7.6 focussed on the continued stakeholder engagement after the project's end and the sustainability of the FOOD 2030 Platform. Reshaping the FOOD 2030 Platform so that it transitions from a one-sided communication tool to a two-way communication platform was proposed. The *‘Sustainable Food Systems Network’* was created. This online, low maintenance digital platform provides more meaningful opportunities for stakeholder engagement. This platform has been built upon to link to the developments of the FIT4FOOD2030 Knowledge Hub, a digital platform that disseminates resources from the project, as well as facilitates interaction between stakeholders.

3.1 The Sustainable Food Systems Network (SFSN)

The Sustainable Food Systems Network (SFSN) primary purpose is to develop a network that supports Task 7.6 and provide a space to create lasting impact and focus on interaction, co-creation and sharing of resources. SFSN is a one-stop shop for stakeholders working to build sustainable food systems. Bringing together policymakers, business professionals, civil society organisations, researchers, NGO/non-profit, funding bodies and citizens all over the world who are working on this emerging topic.

By developing this network, the **long-term vision of the SFSN** is to provide:

- A dedicated single point of contact to effectively promote and share knowledge about food system transformation, R&I, RRI and systems thinking with multiple stakeholders,
- Develop a network of like-minded stakeholders who can share insights across sectors and geographies and ensure new and existing stakeholders with different interests in the project are reached,
- Amplify the outreach and impact of the project’s outputs and activities (e.g. the Knowledge Hub, Inventory of Trends, Final conference, relevant events etc.),
- Ensure continued and increased engagement in the FOOD 2030 platform beyond the life of FIT4FOOD2030,
- Play a facilitating role of ensuring knowledge on food system transformation is accessible and available and users can comment on tools.

3.1.1 Developing the SFSN – The Process

The scoping of Task 7.6 began early in 2019, using the General Assembly meeting as an introduction and brainstorming session on the possible activities that Task 7.6 could encompass. Initially, an online digital platform in the form of a forum providing a space for stakeholders to interact (D7.2) was proposed either by building a platform from scratch or by developing a sub-group related to FIT4FOOD2030 in pre-existing and active online Community of Practices, such as [Food for Cities](#).

On acceptance of the proposal for a ‘Community of Practice’ (CoP)¹ by the project coordinator and consortium, more detailed research commenced. The first action within this phase was researching Community of Practice platforms, pre-existing CoPs and contacting various experts on CoPs, which included administrators of the Data for Nutrition CoP, UNSCN Secretariat, representative from SUN Movement, Dgroups Foundation, ReFresh and CEMAS. From these meetings some conclusions were drawn:

- 1) building a CoP from scratch would require significant amount of time and resources to build properly without bugs and to animate and moderate successfully
- 2) existing, relevant, and active CoPs were difficult to find and when WP7 did find CoPs that were relevant to FIT4FOOD2030, there was no response from moderators or administrators
- 3) the saturation of CoPs within food and nutrition were also mentioned in these meetings as a major barrier to the success of such initiatives. However, many of those are focussing on a single discipline, e.g. ‘nutrition’.
- 4) pursuing the creation of a knowledge management platform, as opposed to a CoP was mentioned as well, as a good fit for the objectives and aims of the task.

As such, WP7 proposed to develop a ‘knowledge hub’ digital platform, that still had similar aims to the CoP, a platform that disseminates resources from the projects and can facilitate two-way interaction between stakeholders. This proposal saw strong synergies between the already established Tools for Transformation working group (WP1, D1.6) and the proposal for Task 7.6.

¹ Community of Practice (CoP) is a group of people who share a common passion for something that they know how to do and who interact regularly to learn how to do it better, e.g. by exchanging information, networking and improving their skills

Step 1. Survey

As part of the ongoing research a [survey](#) was sent out to FIT4FOOD2030 newsletter and FOOD 2030 subscribers, as well as on the EUFIC run SciFoodHealth Twitter page. The aim of the survey was to collect opinions from a variety of stakeholders on their preferences for online community of practices and mailing lists and how the FOOD 2030 Platform could remain relevant and active following the end of the project.

A total of 20 responses were collected, with an overwhelming majority mentioning their interest for joining an online network/community of practice. The responses represented a wide range of stakeholders, with the Scientific Community representing the largest portion (Annex I). Key issues such as food waste, R&I projects related to the farm to fork strategy, healthy and sustainable diets, behavioural transformation of food consumption etc were highlighted and the majority wanted to use the network to connect to a wider network (Annex I).

Step 2. Platform Charter and Functional Requirements

A Platform charter (Annex II) and Platform Netiquette (Annex III) were brainstormed and developed in collaboration between EUFIC and ILSI Europe, along with platform functional specifications (Table 1). These highlight the network's intended mission/vision, as well as its capabilities and interactions for the members. These specifications and visions functioned as a reference point for the decision on which platform to choose.

Table 1. Functional specifications of the platform

Requirement	Summary
Account management	Clear roles and member permission (e.g. account owner, managers, moderators and members)
User interface	Easy to use for both external members and for EUFIC in the back end.
Data management	Compliant with EU data regulation and data management rules.
Monitoring and evaluation	Ability to measure the platform's performance (e.g. access rate, document downloads, shares etc.)
Discussion forum	Ability for members to post and respond to discussions, polls, job advertisements etc. Ability for members to upload content to the platform.
Searchable Content & Members	Ability to search the platform for specific content and also to search for specific members.
Networking	Clear and easy to use membership database and private messaging function.
Events/jobs	Ability to sign up for events and browse through job advertisements.

Step 3. Selection of Platform

Following the functional requirement specifications and the conclusions from meetings with CoP experts, it was decided not to build a platform from scratch, and rather use a pre-existing framework developed by tech companies. EUFIC investigated a variety of different companies, their products and the associated prices and contacted Dgroups Foundation and Mobilize, while Tribe, Hivebrite, Discourse and Vanilla did not meet the criteria, either for price or functionality. Following these enquiries, Mobilize was selected, as their platforms covered all aspects of the functional requirements and had additional benefits such as:

- Linking member's profiles with business-oriented social media platform (i.e. LinkedIn) thereby limiting a hindrance of signing up to an additional platform
- Access to the platform via three pathways: internet browser, mobile application and email

Step 4. Design & Visual Identity

All the original online FIT4FOOD2030 materials share a visual identity, consisting of the logo and colour scheme. As the SFSN was a further development of the FOOD 2030 platform, the FIT4FOOD2030 visual identity was used from the start. The FIT4FOOD2030 logo was chosen to keep brand recognition, especially as the platform would be used for the upcoming [FIT4FOOD2030 Final Conference](#).

Figure 1. Screenshot of SFSN main feed with FIT4FOOD2030 branded logo

Step 5. Launch

The SFSN was soft-launched on 10th July 2020 and on 26th August 2020 for all FIT4FOOD2030 consortium partners to use and test. This involved a 'call for content' whereby FIT4FOOD2030 partners were encouraged to register and upload resources to the site. This was followed by an invitation to the FOOD2030 Platform and FIT4FOOD2030 Newsletter subscribers (Figure 2), which went out on 17th September 2020 in the FIT4FOOD2030 Newsletter. This invitation reached 544 recipients, stimulated 322 opens and 147 clicks. The launch was also published as a news item on the FIT4FOOD2030 website on 16th September 2020 (Figure 3). Lastly, an open invitation to the external audiences was shared on the SciFoodHealth Twitter account on 21st September 2020 (Figure 4). This Twitter post was additionally advertised to reach a broader audience. Two weeks after, the Tweet has gained 36 likes and 25 retweets. These gradual invitations to the network were established to create a gradual community feel prior to the full external public launch. The public launch of the SFSN will be announced on the second day of the FIT4FOOD2030 final conference (25th November 2020).

FOOD 2030 Platform is moving forward - Join us!

That's right! We are excited to announce that the FOOD 2030 Platform has moved to the [Sustainable Food Systems Network](#) hosted on the Mobilize platform and we invite you all to join us!

[Register here](#)

The Network's mission

The mission of this network is to connect, inspire and engage stakeholders working to create sustainable food systems by setting up an active and self-sustained network of people exchanging knowledge and resources on building, researching and communicating about sustainable food systems. Anything from local food production, to research and innovation, to local or national food related policies, you name it, we can discuss it!

Why are we moving?

Good question – the reason why we created this platform is because we want you to really start benefitting from it! Switching to the Sustainable Food Systems Network means that you will be able to:

Figure 2. The official invitation to the SFSN sent to the FOOD2030 Platform and FIT4FOOD2030 Newsletter subscribers

Figure 3. Launch of the Sustainable Food Systems Network published on the FIT4FOOD2030 website as a news item

Figure 4. Twitter post invitation to the Sustainable Food Systems Network

Step 6. Dissemination

Dissemination of the SFSN launch was carried out through the various communication channels and a wide range of platforms. On the official FIT4FOOD2030 website the launch was published as a news item (Figure 3) and a separate webpage was created (Figure 5). The aim of both the news item and webpage was to better explain the vision and mission of the SFSN to the potential members. Besides the already mentioned newsletter and Twitter posts that are directly related to the FIT4FOOD2030 project, the news was communicated to European dietitians through a newsflash by the European Federation of the Associations of Dietitians (EFAD) (Figure 6), and to the dietetic students via the social media and newsletter of the European Network of Dietetic Students (ENDietS). Different actors in the food systems were reached with the EuroFIR AISBL’s eflash news bulletin. Also, the FIT4FOOD2030 project’s partners actively promoted the SFSN through their channels (Figure 7).

Sustainable Food Systems Network

The Sustainable Food Systems Network is a virtual platform where actors interested in the transformation of European food systems can connect, interact and inspire each other.

Register today by filling out [a short registration form!](#)

The Sustainable Food Systems Network has been **initiated in 2020 by the European Commission funded project FIT4FOOD2030**, which advocates for food system transformation through responsible research and innovation (RRI) and the systems approach and has the mission to connect, inspire and engage stakeholders working to build sustainable food systems.

One of the crucial prerequisites for ensuring future-proof food systems is good communication between different stakeholders. Initially, the [FOOD 2030 Platform](#) was responsible for the **mobilisation of a wide variety of food system related stakeholders at the level of cities, regions, countries, and Europe**. It helped to decide research priorities for a sustainable food system. Now, FOOD 2030 Platform has evolved into [Sustainable Food Systems Network \(SFSN\)](#).

Who is the Sustainable Food Systems Network for?

Anyone who wants to be up-to-date with activities aimed at creating **resilient and sustainable food systems with well-integrated responsible research and innovation practices**. It is a place that connects:

- policy makers,
- business professionals,
- civil society organisations,

Figure 5. The Sustainable Food Systems Network webpage published on the official FIT4FOOD2030 website

FIT4FOOD2030 launches the Sustainable Food Systems Network

The EU-funded project [FIT4FOOD2030](#) has recently launched the [Sustainable Food Systems Network](#). It is a virtual platform which aims to connect different actors who are interested in creating sustainable food systems that are ready for future challenges. Since ensuring sustainable and healthy diets is one of the key components of this transformation, dietitians are important actors in the food systems and might benefit from joining as well as contributing to the Network. You can become a part of the Network for free simply by filling out the [registration form](#).

Figure 6. The Sustainable Food Systems Network promotion in EFAD Newsflash

Counting over 600 subscribers and welcoming new members every day, the Sustainable Food Systems Network (SFSN) initiated by the FIT4FOOD2030 project is growing into a reference community for those who have an interest in sustainable food systems - from the research behind it to how to communicate and engage on this topics with different audiences.

This virtual community is hosted on the platform Mobilize and offers different functionalities such as:

- open discussion on a variety of topics from food waste to healthy and sustainable diets, from the impact of food on the climate to the latest innovations
- posting a variety of content like events, surveys and job openings,
- uploading files and resources for easy sharing, and
- contacting directly other platform members.

With such a versatile tool, finding potential collaborators working on a topic

Project

FIT4FOOD2030

FIT4FOOD2030 supports the development and implementation of the European Commission's FOOD 2030 policy framework to transform European food systems towards greater sustainability, resilience, competitiveness and inclusion. The project will integrate existing and emerging networks and infrastructures, creating Communities of Practice that foster RRI and use transformative learning processes to build competences among citizens and stakeholders who are not currently actively integrated in decision-making.

[READ MORE](#)

Figure 7. Promotion of the Sustainable Food Systems Network on the Ecsite website

Step 7. Engagement

To ensure the continuation of the SFSN and the possibility for as many members to reap its benefits, an engagement plan was created and implemented. This process is still ongoing at the time of submission of this deliverable and will last until the end of 2020. From 2021 onwards, EUFIC will continue to build on the network, particularly in the context of its other/future EU-funded projects, and encourage other consortium partners to do the same; the network is open and all its members have access to it. It is expected that the SFSN will increasingly become an independent self-sustained network of individuals interested in the cross-sharing of knowledge and resources related to food systems and responsible research and innovation.

The engagement plan consists of

- 1) researching the members' areas of interest and expertise,
- 2) stimulating engagement focused on their areas of interest,
- 3) disseminating the FIT4FOOD2030 project's outcomes, and
- 4) creating engagement and networking around the FIT4FOOD2030 final conference.

First and third steps are currently in progress. Second and fourth steps are upcoming.

Areas of members' interest and expertise were explored by posting 2 questions on the 2 consecutive weeks (Figure 8 and 9). The question "What topics are you most interested in?" was posted on 7th October, and by 13th October got 149 responses. The question "What type of engagement are you most interested in?" was posted on 12th October, and by 13th October got 91 responses. From the beginning, the response rate was relatively high and engagement with the poll questions indicated that the implementation of an engagement plan was needed to give a platform more specific direction. The early results show that members on the Sustainable Food Systems Network are most interested in:

- sustainable food production, local food production, healthy and sustainable diets;
- past and upcoming events, collaboration opportunities and scientific articles, various tools and resources.

What topics are you most interested in?

302 149 [See all analytics](#)

There are almost over 600 members on the Sustainable Food Systems Network, from business professionals and policy makers to citizens. To make this network more beneficial to its members, we would like to know what your main interests are and what you would like to see more of on the Sustainable Food Systems Network. Check the boxes next to the area(s) of your interest.

Figure 8. Realisation of an engagement plan for the Sustainable Food Systems Network – 1st question

What type of engagement are you most interested in?

244 91 [See all analytics](#)

Thank you all for a great response and sharing your areas of interest with this community. To additionally help you get more curated content, I would kindly like to ask you to answer which type of engagement you are most interested in to see here. You can check as many boxes as you want.

Also, if you have any comments, suggestions or questions, let us know!

Figure 9. Realisation of an engagement plan for the Sustainable Food Systems Network – 2nd question

fit4food2030.eu - #FOOD2030EU

Discussion and dialogue are necessary drivers of change. One of SFSN’s advantages to leverage is the ability to post comments and send private messages. After getting a more detailed insight into the interests of members, the engagement plan involves sharing and encouraging the sharing of the content matching the interests and expertise identified on the platform with an aim to strengthen the connection and cooperation between members as well as to secure the longevity of the Sustainable Food Systems Network. The additional steps are sharing the project’s outcomes (Figure 10) and promotion materials for the final conference (Figure 11). In the run-up to the final conference, which will take place on 24th and 25th November 2020, all speakers and their sessions will be promoted using the visual template which contains their image, name with affiliations, and quote with the main message or a brief description of their presentation. Many valuable outcomes emerged from the FIT4FOOD2030 project therefore the Sustainable Food Systems Network can be used as a facilitator in the dissemination of various webinars, policy briefs, tools and guidelines.

Free webinar series available online - "Towards sustainable food systems through Research and Innovation"

115 10 See all analytics

Hi all,

Welcome to all the new members! Its really exciting to see this network grow and I look forward to following along in the discussions and resources posted over time.

I want to draw your attention to the free webinar series titled "**Towards sustainable food systems through Research and Innovation**", that happened between March - June 2020. This was produced by the FIT4FOOD2030 project to advocate for responsible research and innovation and systems thinking for food system transformation. With some amazing guest speakers, series explores the project as a case study to using R&I policy for food system transformation at the level of cities, regions, countries and the EU. The series explored the following topics:

- RRI in food systems
- Cities as change aagents: building competences for future food systems
- Transforming our food systems: Research and Innovation as an enabler of the Farm to Fork Strategy
- RRI in policy making for future-proof food systems.

Recordings are [available here](#).

Figure 10. Sharing the project’s outcomes on the Sustainable Food Systems Network

Dr. Veronica Maria Teresa Lattanzio
Chemist, Senior Researcher at the Institute of Sciences of Food Production – National Research Council of Italy

*„Let’s strengthen trust in the EU Food Safety System!
Contribute to co-creating new strategies, speeding digitalization and boosting transparent communication to shape the Food Safety System of the future!”*

#FIT4FOOD2030
#FOOD2030EU

Figure 11. A visual template for the promotion of the FIT4FOOD2030 final conference on the SFSN

3.2 FIT4FOOD2030 Knowledge Hub (Tools for Transformation)

As part of D1.6, Work Package 1 (WP1 - Methodology to build the FOOD2030 Platform) established a working group on Tools for Transformation to focus the project’s efforts in the final year on the tools and developing a toolkit; the WP7 leader was involved in this initiative. The aim of the working group was to develop an online repository for the several tools and guidelines that have been produced by the project. The proposal for a repository of tools had strong synergies with the established tasks of 7.6 as outlined in D7.2; as such, EUFIC’s contribution to it has undertaken as part of WP7’s efforts in D7.5 (i.e. creation of a toolkit to showcase the project’s outputs).

3.2.1 FIT4FOOD2030 Knowledge Hub – The process

The scoping of the Tools for Transformation with the working group began in the beginning of 2019, followed by the establishment of the group in the General Assembly. WP1 presented the idea of a repository either made available via 1) FIT4FOOD2030 website or 2) existing platforms. An advantage of using the FIT4FOOD2030 website was that the tools could be showcased in a uniform format and thereby the working group could design their own entry points and search engine. While using existing platforms would provide an existing and wide audience base from the start, finding relevant platforms proved to be difficult. The working group took the decision to create a database or repository of the tools from scratch on the FIT4FOOD2030 website. The developers of the FIT4FOOD2030 website were chosen to carry out the work.

3.2.2 Visual Identity

Similar to the SFSN, the visual design of the Knowledge Hub was to reflect the FIT4FOOD2030 branding and provide clear visual clues to the content of the platform. This was also carried over into the templates for the different tools (Annex IV). A group of icons were specifically developed for the platform to represent various categories and types of tools. These icons have been used to represent the categories on [the tools for transformation page](#) and the types of tools on the main website [homepage](#).

Figure 12. FIT4FOOD2030 and Knowledge Hub Icons

An additional logo was developed over the course of the project, representing the ability of the tool to be used in an online format. Titled ‘Digital-proof’, the stamp was initiated following the COVID-19 pandemic, when it became increasingly clear and difficult for City and Food Labs to test the tools physically and were thus forced to test them online. This logo can be found on the tools that have been tested and are available to use online.

Figure 13. Digital-proof logo

3.2.3 Name and Domain

The initial suggestion for the platform was ‘Tools for Transformation’. Other names considered included “FIT4FOOD2030 Community”, “FOOD 2030 Knowledge Hub”, “FIT4FOOD2030 Repository”. It was collectively decided that the platform would be titled “FIT4FOOD2030 Knowledge Hub”, with the collective group of tools called “Tools for Transformation” represented by a page on the Knowledge Hub. The domain name of the platform is: www.knowledgehub.fit4food2030.eu.

3.2.4 Design

The FIT4FOOD2030 Knowledge Hub was designed to provide a user interface suitable for both tablet and desktop formats. The main site navigation consists of the following:

- Home
- About
- Tools for Transformation
- Contact

These allow the users to navigate the site through a top-level section on the website. The navigation is present on all pages of the website. Below, a summary of the purpose of the ‘Tools for Transformation’ and individual tool pages is available.

Figure 14. The Knowledge Hub website navigation bar

3.2.5 Tools for Transformation

The most critical page on the Knowledge Hub is [the Tools for Transformation page](#) as it allows for searching and gaining access to the practical outputs of the FIT4FOOD2030 project and represents the core of the website. The page's purpose is to act as a resource repository, supporting users in accessing all of the tools developed by the project. It is the single access point for all FIT4FOOD2030 tools and guidelines. Through browsing or specific searches can access the free to use and download tools.

The page is designed so that users access the tools either through the four main categories, tailored to specific needs: (1) Running a food or living lab; (2) Explore and understanding the food system; (3) Improving R&I policy coherence and alignment; (4) Educating or training people on food system transformation or through accessing all the tools at once (Figure 15). Users can then further refine their search for tools through the filter based on for 6 different types of tools, 9 target audience and keywords (Figure 16). The library of tools is dynamic, and it is possible to upload new tools as they are developed.

Figure 15. Screenshot of the Tools for Transformation page and the four tailored categories

Figure 16. Screenshot of filter

3.2.6 Individual Tool pages

Once a user has found their desired tool in the 'Tools for Transformation', they can then review the summary and pdf attached to the specific tool. To access this, the user accesses the individual tool summary page. This page was designed to provide the user with the following information in order to make an assessment of the resource and decide if it is useful to them:

- summary overview of the tool
- keywords/tags related to the tool
- category(ies) related to the tool
- sharing via social networks (Facebook, twitter, LinkedIn etc.)
- download button of the pdf
- contact name and email address for the FIT4FOOD2030 partner responsible for the tool
- related tools
- image of the front page of the pdf containing further information (i.e. duration, audience, developer)
- comment section

Figure 17. Screenshot of individual tool page

The comment section on the platform was specifically added to increase engagement with the tools and allow users to provide their experiences and updates to the tools.

Leave A Comment

Logged in as [EUFIC EUFIC](#). [Log out »](#)

Comment...

[POST COMMENT](#)

Figure 18. Screenshot of comments

3.2.7 Collecting Tools

Tools and guidelines were developed across the whole breadth of the FIT4FOOD2030 work packages (WP) and therefore at the initial stage, the working group developed [a survey](#) which was sent out to all WP leaders to identify all relevant tools for the repository. WP leaders responded with 52 different tools, these were then carried over to a Google sheet document, where a further 26 tools were added.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
		Filter/ "What can the tool be used for?"	Type of tool	Target Audience "For whom? Who will be the end-user of this tool?"	Keywords (max - 10; see google survey for the non-exhaustive list)	Please specify to which larger tool (1 or 2) the tools you are describing corresponds to. Please write the title here.	Other related tools (this will be on the individual tool page)	Submitted to the google form by	Responsible for the tool type	Responsible to make the tool	Deadline
1											
2		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To explore and understand the food system To educate or train people on food system transformation 	Communication tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitators Policy makers Researchers Businesses Funders Students Non Governmental Organisations / Civil Society Professionals 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Food system Responsible research and innovation Food 2030 Video Webinar Policy Nutrition Co-creation Digital-proof tool Innovation 	None	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FIT4FOOD2030: System Thinking, System Innovation and System Transformation Policy brief #1 A Systems Approach to Research and Innovation for Food System Transformation (#1 update) RRI in food systems Cities as Change agents: building competences for future food systems: Webinar #2 Transforming our food systems: research and innovation as an enabler of the farm to fork strategy: Webinar #3 RRI in policy making for future-proof food systems: Webinar #4 				
3		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To work with communities (to run a Lab) To educate or train people on food system transformation 	Communication tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitator Policy makers Researchers Students NGO/CSO Professionals 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Policy Network building Food system approach City and Food Labs Webinar Stimulating change Responsible Research and Innovation Multi-stakeholder 	None	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RRI in the food systems: Webinar #1 Transforming our food systems: Research and innovation as an enabler of the farm to fork strategy: Webinar #3 RRI in policy making for future-proof food systems: Webinar #4 	EUFIC	Cathrine	Cathrine	31 July 2020

Figure 19. Screenshot of Google Sheet of Tool collection

3.2.8 Developing the Tagging Taxonomy

Using the Google sheet (Figure 19), WP7 in collaboration with the developers created the tagging taxonomy. The tagging taxonomy that is now used covers the following filters:

- **Type of tool:** covering the purposes of the various tools from; setting up communities, developing self-sustained networks, food (R&I) policy alignment, educational modules, food system trends, showcases and breakthroughs
- **Target Audience:** i.e. Facilitators, NGO, policymakers, researchers, students
- **Keywords:** i.e. FOOD 2030 topics (Climate, Nutrition, Innovation, Circularity), food waste, RRI, R&I, digital-proof tool
- **Categories:** see Figure 15

3.2.9 Access and Data Security

Access to the backend of the Hub was only granted to Hub administrators which include the WP Leaders involved in the working group. One of the main aims of the FIT4FOOD2030 Knowledge Hub is also to encourage cross-sharing of information, as such the comment section on the individual tools was developed. Users have the opportunity to comment on the tools either anonymously or with their name. To prevent any risk, the Hub

has been integrated with reCaptcha to prevent any malicious software. The backend of the website also allows for the working team to delete any comments not deemed relevant to the content of the page.

3.2.10 Monitoring and Evaluation

For monitoring purposes, a Google Tag Manager was installed to help analyse how many of the tools have been downloaded. Until 13th October 2020 tools have been downloaded 113 times in total.

3.2.11 Timeline and Testing Phases

An initial timeline was developed with the aim of finalising the Hub by the beginning of September. However, over the course of the summer months it became clear that many tools from various WPs still needed to be finalised. As WP7 and the website developers had completed the architecture of the website, it was decided that WP7 would provide a How-to document and tutorial on uploading new tools. This was presented on 10th September 2020. This would also allow for more tools to be uploaded after the project's end (see Section No. 5. Impact, outreach & sustainability).

The testing of the Knowledge Hub involved two phases: an Alpha- and a Beta-phase.

- **Alpha:** Initially EUFIC servers hosted the platform, where WP7 and the working team conducted the initial tests on the platform. These tests resulted in structural changes and smaller content-based revisions.
- **Beta:** In this phase consortium members were asked to provide their thoughts and feedback either via email or through the comment section on the Knowledge Hub. This was the last round of feedback to be incorporated into the platform and involved minor structural changes.
- **Further testing:** WP1 may test further with external stakeholders following a similar process to the beta-testing.

4. Key Audience(s)

In line with the objective of the plan for continued communication between stakeholders, namely, to engage stakeholders in a targeted and meaningful way in the challenging times to come, the Sustainable Food Systems Network and the Knowledge Hub are tailored towards specific audiences, i.e. stakeholders within food systems primarily in Europe but also worldwide. Even though these two platforms are a result of the same project and both target similar stakeholders, the Knowledge Hub has a more specific key audience depending on the various tools and resources located there.

The Sustainable Food Systems Network is an extension of the Task 7.2 (Development and implementation of multi-level stakeholder engagement plan), therefore the target audiences are related to the communication and dissemination plan described in the Deliverable 7.1. Target audiences include primarily local, national and European policy makers and implementers, and Academia, but also citizens and consumers, funding agencies, NGOs and CSOs, school children and students, businesses and industry, knowledge and education centres.

On the other hand, the Tools for Transformation within the interactive Knowledge Hub are divided into categories according to the specific audiences they are intended for, which makes it easier for stakeholders to engage. There are 15 target audiences, including researchers, facilitators, policy makers, professionals, funders, NGOs and CSOs, businesses, students, intermediaries of food system transformation, lab coordinators, policy lab coordinators, teachers, secondary school children, general public, and organisations. However, it is worth noting that stakeholders will eventually have multiple roles and therefore be able to use many of the tools.

5. Impact, outreach & sustainability

The expected impact of this work can be articulated in short-, mid- and long-term parameters and outcomes.

In the short term, impact can be measured by:

- the number of members registering to the Sustainable Food Systems Network and the level of engagement via posts created, resources uploaded, polls conducted, and jobs advertised, as well as
- the number of downloads of tools from the FIT4FOOD2030 Knowledge Hub and engagement via comments on the resources.

While the FIT4FOOD2030 Knowledge Hub is not yet live, the engagement in Sustainable Food Systems Network – still before its official launch during the final conference on 25 November 2020 – has clearly shown a great interest with 639 members at the time of the submission of this Deliverable (15 October 2020).

In a more mid- to long-term outlook, the expected impacts will revolve around the further development of both the Knowledge Hub and Sustainable Food Systems Network. The main challenge for the Knowledge Hub is to keep it alive after the end of the project. With a goal to extend its impact and adoption of the tools, the Knowledge Hub will be transferred to the server of the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, the project coordinator has committed to continue managing the platform. Besides that, different communication channels that were used during the project's duration will be interconnected. The Knowledge Hub will be linked on the FIT4FOOD2030 official website as a key project output.

EUFIC, on the other hand, will continue to build and expand on the Sustainable Food Systems Network via stakeholder engagement activities in its other/future EU-funded and EUFIC projects, all of which have a link with food and health, ranging from plant-based protein, to the microbiome, to sustainable food packaging. The expected impact is twofold: one, building on an existing network avoids starting new communities from scratch, which will likely become dormant/inactive when the project stops; two, by bringing together an even more diverse spectrum of stakeholders (through different projects that have a link to food, health and sustainability), it facilitates the systems approach that FIT4FOOD2030 is strongly advocating for. FIT4FOOD2030 has made it possible to purchase a five-year licence, which offers a great opportunity to valorise this network, and EUFIC is committed to secure resources to 'keep it alive' also after that period. Although EUFIC is the platform's administrator, all members can freely use and access the network, resources, and functionalities, including the starting of discussions, promoting research/events/job ads, and initiating polls. A benefit of such a platform, besides facilitating outreach between stakeholders, is that it is low maintenance, increasing the likelihood of sustainability.

Finally, on a long term, the wished-for impacts are a higher uptake of RRI and City and Policy Lab type of methods to facilitate engagement with stakeholders in the policy making process, and, ultimately, improved European food systems. It would, of course, be somewhat presumptuous to believe that these two platforms alone would lead to a better food system, but our mindset and belief is that they will be used, sustained and moderated, according to FIT4FOOD2030's principles, and will make a contribution to this endeavour, no matter how small.

Annex I. Results of a survey sent to the FIT4FOOD2030 Stakeholder list

What stakeholder category would you define yourself as?

20 responses

Figure 1. Stakeholder categories for Survey

In what sector do you operate?

20 responses

Figure 2. Stakeholder Sectors for Survey

If you joined the CoP or mailing list what would you like to use it for?

20 responses

Figure 3. What would stakeholders use the Community of Practice for?

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Annex II. Platform Charter

Table from Sustainable Food System Network Charter document

Platform Charter	
<p>What is the purpose of the community—including its value, primary scope, and goals?</p>	<p>The Sustainable Food System Platform/Network will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Become a continuation of the FOOD2030 platform created by the FIT4FOOD2030 project. - Be a one-stop-shop for stakeholders working on this emerging topic to access and upload tools and resources, events, engage in discussions to learn from each other and share best practices. Thereby, contributing to building the expertise and - Raise awareness of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and Research and Innovation (R&I). - To contribute to building competences and expertise of sustainable food systems and R&I researchers, entrepreneurs and policy makers. - To advance the analysis and discussion of key topics, capitalizing on the competencies and experiences of its members. - Facilitate networking, joint research initiatives with a view to produce knowledge
<p>What value does it bring?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bringing the relevant disciplines/silos together to allow for a systems approach • Access to expertise • Access to free-of-charge resources • Help with challenges • Meaningful participation • Engagement/fun with colleagues • Meaningful participation • Professional development • Network
<p>Vision/Mission?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Our vision is an active and self-sustained network of people exchanging knowledge on building, researching, and

	<p>communicating about sustainable food systems.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Our mission is to connect, inspire and engage stakeholders working to build sustainable food systems.
Who are its members?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open membership • Stakeholders working to build sustainable food systems (policy makers, business professionals, civil society organizations, academics and NGO/non-profit and funding bodies)
How will members be recruited?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onboarding of FOOD2030 platform subscribers • Social media promotion SciFoodHealth, ILSI, F4F communication partners • Newsletter to PROTEIN2FOOD Consortium • Introduction text to other EU project newsletters (Pro-future, Fox, Smartchain, Strength2Food)
How will the platform be organised and run?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EUFIC and ILSI until December 2020 • EUFIC take over from there to be incorporated into other projects • Develop schedule of tasks/content from August-December with clear indications of who will contribute • Ask for consortium buy-in on commenting/posting • Ask about FOOD2030 stakeholder list
Who will take key responsibilities? (Core team roles) & how much time to dedicate?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EUFIC and ILSI • Tasks will be divided up through schedule and list of tasks with clear indication of who does what
What are the desired behaviours of the membership?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trust, respect, collaboration, reciprocity, network/idea/resource sharing, listening, open & honest discussions
What strategy (tools, facilitation, norms, incentives) will be used to generate the desired behaviours?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome post that describes desired behaviours • “Netiquette” document in file folder • Posting of content 1 time a week?
What are the resources needed— including budget?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No other monetary costs other than Mobilize platform price are foreseen

Annex III. Platform Netiquette

1. **Participate**, in the shared learning environment and gain the maximum benefit from this platform by connecting with the rest of the members.
2. **Help Others**, you may have more experience than the person next to you. Give them a hand, they will appreciate it!
3. **Be Patient**, not everyone will know these rules before posting, try to be understanding of others and their opinions and perspectives.
4. **Cite your sources**, when sharing ideas, papers, reports originating from someone else.
5. **Respect Diversity and other opinions**, do not use language that is - or that could be understood to be - offensive toward others.
6. **Be brief**, stay on topic and refrain from posting irrelevant links, comments, thoughts or pictures.
7. **Be respectful** to all members of this platform, whether you agree or not.
8. **Be aware of strong language, all caps and exclamation points**, these can be misread and misunderstood.
9. **Be careful with humour and sarcasm**, these can also be misread and misunderstood.

Thank you for your attention and happy posting!

Annex IV. Template for the Tools for Transformation

Screenshot of Tools for Transformation template

COMMUNICATION TOOL

The importance of women in leadership roles throughout the food system | Corinna Hawkes

Corinna Hawkes
Director of Centre for Food Policy, City University, London

The importance of women in leadership roles throughout the food system | Corinna Hawkes

In a nutshell

In this interview, Corinna Hawkes, Professor at City, University of London, talks about the importance of women in leadership roles throughout the food system. Action is needed throughout the food supply system so that the entire system becomes reoriented towards healthy diets and sustainable food systems.

<h4 style="text-align: center;">What for?</h4> <p>To explore and understand the food system To educate or train people on food system transformation</p>	<h4 style="text-align: center;">How long?</h4> <p>1:28 minutes</p>
<h4 style="text-align: center;">For whom?</h4> <p>Facilitators, Policy makers, Researchers, Businesses, Funders, Students, NGOs/ CSOs, Professionals</p>	<h4 style="text-align: center;">Created by</h4> <p>EUFIC</p>

Something to share?

Leave us a comment about this tool on [the platform](#).
This tool was developed as part of FIT4FOOD2030 project, see this tool and others on the [FIT4FOOD2030 Knowledge Hub](#).

Date of creation: October 2019
How to cite?

Hawkes, C. (2019). The importance of women in leadership roles throughout the food system | Corinna Hawkes.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hQWJr8vAyPw&t=14s>

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